

HYDROCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE BOTEVGRAD BASIN, BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT: The qualitative characterization of groundwater within the watershed of Botevgrad Basin is determined through statistical and spatial analysis of 156 water sources. A GIS database has been compiled, calculations and area studies have been made, providing an up-to-date idea of the groundwater quality of the Quaternary aquifer in Botevgrad Basin, which is poorly studied. The water sources are localized and categorized according to aquifer types. Boreholes with deep recharge are examined separately. The predominant total mineralization is below 1g/L and the groundwater is classified as fresh. The statistical analysis of the data using the ArcGIS tools allow to establish spatial regularities in the change of the chemical composition of the studied indicators. Maps have been created on the basis of the results, which allow to characterise the chemical composition of groundwater and to locate water sources with anomalous contents of some components due to natural and anthropogenic factors.

Key words: groundwater, hydrochemical characteristics, GIS, Botevgrad Basin

INTRODUCTION

Groundwater is part of the natural environment and has its own local and regional specificity related to quantitative accumulation, dynamics, regime, and hydrochemical properties. Deterioration of their quality is a real problem in many regions around the world. Industrial waste, the use of pesticides and chemicals and other pollutants can cause serious harm to the environment and human health. The quality of groundwater depends on various factors. There is a close relationship between groundwater and the rocks with which it is in prolonged contact during its formation. Climate change and water use are the two main factors contributing to the depletion of water resources.

The Botevgrad Basin is located in Western Bulgaria. Its watershed area is 488 km². It includes 10 villages and the towns of Pravets and Botevgrad. Groundwater in the Botevgrad Basin is of vital importance for meeting the needs of local residents and for the development of industry and agriculture. The qualities of groundwater in the area are insufficiently studied. In the monograph "Groundwater in the Republic of Bulgaria" by Antonov & Danchev (1980), the waters in the Botevgrad Basin (Quaternary aquifer) are described as fresh. According to hydrochemical indicators, they are suitable for use in industry, drinking water supply, and irrigation.

The objective of the present research is to obtain an idea of the spatial regularities in the chemical composition of the groundwater in the Botevgrad Basin, based on the available hydrochemical information, with focus on the Quaternary pore aquifer in view of its importance for water supply to the population in the area, as well as the fact that the information about this aquifer is comparatively abundant.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Chemical test data were collected to determine the quality of groundwater in the Botevgrad Basin. The methods used in the present study have been applied to determine local groundwater hydrochemistry in other regions of Bulgaria, as discussed by Toteva & Shanov (2021), Mihaylova et al. (2022). Based on the surveyed water sources, a study area covering the majority of the Botevgrad Basin was outlined (Fig. 1).

Coordinates of the sampled water sources were inputted from a map showing their locations, which had been previously georeferenced. The present study was based on data for 156 water sources, including wells, springs, boreholes, streams, intakes and shaft wells. Most chemical analyses are taken from a report by Segmenski & Dobriyanov on hydrogeological surveys of the Botevgrad Basin (1969-1973). A table was compiled with data from chemical test reports for groundwater in the watershed of Botevgrad Basin. Each sample was assigned a number for more precise analyses. A database was compiled with tables, graphs of relationships between total mineralization, chemical compounds, and elements, vector layers and raster images.

Figure 1. Hydrogeological map of Botevgrad Basin showing sampled water sources and zones of elevated nitrate content.

Based on the information about groundwater in relation to the host rocks by Malinkova et al. (2023), groundwater has been identified in sedimentary, karst, and fissure rocks. From the table of chemical data analyses, 13 boreholes were selected and analysed independently of the other water sources, as they reveal groundwater from deeper levels that formed under the Quaternary aquifer. These boreholes have depths of approximately 100 m or more. Minimum, maximum and average values of total mineralization, temperature, pH, major and minor components of groundwater were calculated. A Piper diagram has been constructed. The zones with data for $\text{NO}_3^- > 50 \text{ mg/L}$ have been visualized.

RESULTS

The average temperature of groundwater is around 13°C and the pH ranges from slightly acidic to slightly alkaline, with neutral pH predominating. The total mineralization of groundwater is up to 1 g/L for most water sources. Exception are two water sources located in the southern part of the Medven heights (520 m) near the village of Skravena. Water samples from these show total mineralization slightly above 1 g/L (1.06 g/L). The groundwater is mostly HCO_3^- -Ca type, and to a lesser extent SO_4^- -Ca-Mg type (Fig. 2). A significant exceptions are water samples from 3 boreholes located between the villages Novachane and Skravena and a water source from the southern part of the Medven elevation, where groundwater is sodium-sulfate. Zones with expected nitrate contents above 50 mg/L are delineated, for two water sources located in the southern part of the Medven heights, nitrate values reach $223 - 283 \text{ mg/L}$. The total mineralisation varies from 0.9 g/L to 1.06 g/L in the zones of elevated content of nitrate, iron and manganese.

Figure 2. Piper diagram of water sources by water types in the watershed of the Botevgrad Basin

Results from chemical analyses include microelements Ag, Al, As, Ba, Cu, Ga, Fe, Mn, Mo, Ni, Pb, Sr, Ti, Zn. The statistical data processing is presented in Figure 3. Most samples show elevated levels of Al, with values reaching up to 3.57 mg/L. In one analysis of As, a value of 2.6 mg/L was obtained. In terms of microelements, maximum values were recorded for Fe - 1.82 mg/L, Mn - 0.86 mg/L, and Pb - 0.15 mg/L.

The groundwater in all boreholes with deep recharge is low-temperature type (11°C - 14°C) with neutral to slightly alkaline pH. The total mineralization is below 1 g/L in those boreholes. The groundwater in them varies from bicarbonate-calcium to sodium-sulfate types, with a trend from west to east as a result of change in the host rocks and underlying rocks at the base of the boreholes. Sodium-sulfate type waters are characteristic of the area between the villages Novachane and Skravena and the Medven heights. Fluoride (8 - 11 mg/L) is observed in the boreholes between the villages Novachane and Skravena and the Medven heights, from which relatively deeper groundwater is abstracted. Fluoride in anomalous content is an indicator for mineral waters.

Figure 3. Minimum, maximum, and mean values of microelements in the watershed of the Botevgrad Basin

DISCUSSION

The application of GIS in processing hydrochemical indicators provides an opportunity to update and provide a further level of detail in hydrochemical regularities and peculiarities of groundwater in the studied area. The qualitative characterization of waters in the Botevgrad Basin watershed is incomplete since not the entire area has been explored. The Danube River Basin Directorate has designated, near the village Novachane, one point for monitoring water quality in the quaternary aquifer in the Botevgrad Basin, which is considered insufficient. Between the villages Litakovo and Radotina, groundwater in karst and fractured rocks with higher circulation are slightly alkaline (pH 8.4 - 8.9). The slightly acidic waters (pH 5.4 - 6.2) above the village Litakovo and in the northern part of the Medven heights according to Segmenski & Dobriyanov (1969-1973) are associated with local manifestations of concentrated pyritic ore occurrences.

In general, there are no significant differences in the chemical composition of fresh groundwater formed in different types of rocks (sedimentary, karst, fissure). The variation in the values of the hydrochemical indicators is due to the specific hydrogeological conditions at each sampled point (depth of groundwater, features of the unsaturated zone, flow direction, anthropogenic factors, etc.). Based on total mineralization values below 1 g/L, groundwater in the study area can be classified as fresh. In most of the surveyed water sources, the water type is bicarbonate-calcium, exceptions being groundwater from boreholes between Novachane and Skravena villages and the southern part of the Medven heights, where there is a transition to sodium-sulfate type. The area is highly fractured. The Dragoybalkan Fault is located near Novachane, and there is a possibility of mixing fresh waters with deeper, more mineralized waters. Zones of elevated nitrate values in porous aquifers are likely due to the use of fertilizers and pesticides in agriculture. Nitrates can be leached from the soil by rainfall infiltration into groundwater. Two zones with high nitrate values have been identified: the Medven heights (283 mg/L) and approximately 1 km west of Litakovo (over 180 mg/L). The groundwater is in fractured trachyandesites and gabrodiorites. Increased concentrations of Fe and Mn are observed in the Medven heights. Along the faults it is possible that mixing may be occurring, with more mineralized waters from depth, where the water exchange is slow and the conditions are reducing. Further sampling and hydrogeological investigation are needed to clarify the situation. Elevated aluminum values may be explained by the presence of host rocks rich in aluminum compounds (silicates). During natural dissolution and filtration processes, aluminum compounds dissolve into groundwater and test results can show elevated aluminium concentrations if the water is not filtered in the course of sampling. In the area between Novachane and Skravena villages, arsenic levels ranging

from 0.023 mg/L to 2.6 mg/L have been reported. The geological formations in this area comprise shales, aleurolites, argillites, as well as alluvial and deluvial deposits. These may naturally have high arsenic concentrations. The elevated arsenic concentrations may also be the result of anthropogenic pollution. The higher concentrations of Pb, observed west of the village Gurkovo, are likely due to anthropogenic pollution.

CONCLUSION

As a result of the present study, a hydrochemical characterization of groundwater in the Botevgrad Basin has been compiled. Elevated concentrations of certain indicators are observed in limited areas. Zones differing from the overall hydrochemistry of groundwater in the region have been identified. In localized areas with numerous faults, mixing of fresh waters with deeper groundwater likely occurs along these faults, where the water exchange is slow and the redox conditions are reducing. The graphical analyses and maps compiled on the basis of collected water source data, provide prognostic and anticipated results for the chemical composition of groundwater within the watershed of Botevgrad Basin. Further studies are needed to clarify the hydrochemical regime and carry out more detailed investigations of the identified sites in the Quaternary aquifer – Botevgrad Basin with anomalous chemical indicator values.

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